

Oral presentation

Effects of lake shape on Titan air-sea interaction

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The Cassini-Huygens mission brought unprecedented insights into Titan's methane cycle, revealing methane lakes and seas, clouds and riverbeds, and evidence of rain. However, questions remain about the presence of methane reservoirs and their connection to clouds and precipitation. To better understand the methane cycle, we investigate physical processes with a mesoscale climate model. The first step focuses on the evaporation above methane lakes, providing insights into the quantity of evaporated methane and its transport by local winds. This investigation began with the 2D mtWRF model (Rafkin & Soto, 2020), that showed that the canonical circulation over a methane lake on Titan is a lake breeze blowing at the surface from the lake to the land. We then added heating/cooling by solar and infrared radiation in the model (Chatain et al., 2022). We observed strong diurnal and seasonal variations in the intensity and propagation of the lake breeze, which also affect the methane evaporation and the lake temperature. Our latest improvement – presented here – is the addition of a third dimension to the model. In particular, this improvement creates differences in how the simulated circulation preserves mass-continuity. 2D simulations are equivalent to a lake with an infinite extension along one dimension. In 3D simulations configured with an idealized circular lake, results are notably different, especially on the wind circulation. Due to divergence of the air mass moving away from the lake at the surface, the lake breeze extends less over land in 3D. In contrast, due to convergence of the air mass at altitude, the subsidence over the lake is twice as strong in 3D. 3D simulations performed with a background wind lead to the formation of a pocket of strongly accelerated wind behind the lake, which was not observed in 2D simulations. We also investigate the effect of irregular shorelines for realistic lakes, compared to the idealized circular lakes. Over the realistic lake, surface wind and evaporation rate are enhanced in inlets, and decreased around peninsulas. At a few hundred meters in altitude, stronger winds form over the land on peninsulas. Simulations with several lakes show interactions between the lake's breezes, leading to resulting circulations that are quite complex and difficult to predict in the absence of 3D modeling. Winds and humidity increase with the size of the lake, reaching near-saturation values for the largest ones. We conclude that even though they are computationally more expensive, 3D simulations are necessary to get accurate values for the winds and evaporation rates of Titan's lakes.